

From Stravinsky to Starbucks: Learning from Classical Music to Create Better Service Experiences

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Abstract

As a relatively new discipline, service design has a lot to learn from various fields that have well-established histories. This paper will briefly explore the field of classical music and draw aspects from it that are useful in thinking about service design. Themes will also be drawn from music in an attempt to provide applicable approaches to service design. The topics that will be paralleled are the following: how services can be thought of as performances, how the roles inherent to music find similarities to roles defined in service design, and how music notation systems are essential in connecting different music roles together and why service design should adopt a notation system of its own.

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A Background on Services

We live and breathe services. From when we wake up to when we sleep, services surround us at all times of the day. The service sector has now become nearly 65% of U.S. GDP, and comprises 80% of U.S. employment (USTR Focus on Services, n.d.). Before service industries captured the economy, the manufacturing industry dominated, and good product design kept companies afloat. Extensive product development processes were established; products became successful when they were designed with usefulness, usability and desirability in mind. So, if products have such an extensive design and development process, why are service design's development processes so lacking? Services are not new, and yet designers have only recently started to think about how we can bring design to services.

For the purposes of this paper, services have a set of core concepts that distinguish them from products. First, services involve both tangible and intangible aspects. While products revolve around an artifact, services are not limited to physical items. For example, a hotel customer will take away almost nothing but the experience of their stay, an intangible good. Second, services are co-created; they require customers in order for them to exist. A hair salon could not provide services if customers never showed up, but manufacturing plants could keep making tables and chairs even if no one wanted them. Lastly, with services, it becomes the service provider's responsibility to provide value of a service to the customer. The service provider has control of their service offering throughout the entire engagement in contrast to products, where customers generally have freedom with what they want to do with an item. Because of these differences, it becomes clearer that designing services requires a different set of approaches than with product design.

A different way of looking at services

Services are often discussed as a delivery of a set of actions or products from the service provider to the customer. If thought about in this way, services are much like performances in the performing arts. In the performing arts, creating a performance depends on two important aspects: the people involved in the performance, and the tools involved in creating and maintaining the work. For example, it would be hard to create a good movie if there were no film scripts for actors to follow, or if the sound editors and directors never communicated throughout the production process. For this paper, I will be looking at services through a similar lens (see Figure 1). While there are many fields to look to in the performing arts, I will draw inspiration from classical music. Classical music has a long and established history in terms of the roles and tools in the creation of any musical performance, and many pointers can be taken from music to be applied to service design.

Figure 1: Relationship between service, people, and tools

I will be looking at classical music and services in three parts. First, I will be discussing services as performances. Next I will approach the roles contained within music and services. Lastly, I will look at the tools behind creating musical performances and services.

Performance

There are three aspects of music performances that are applicable when thinking about services: music working as a system, music impressions, and music styles.

Music and service as systems

Music and services both exist as entire systems. At the micro level, music is made up of a series of notes, pauses, and rhythms, strung together to create melodies. At the macro level, it is made up of those melodies, as well as different themes and patterns. Successful pieces are those that can make all the micro and macro level parts work together to form one coherent piece of work.

Services consist of a series of interactions across many different places, called ‘touchpoints’. With services, the micro level exists as individual touchpoints of a service and the components that make up that touchpoint, and the macro level exists as the connection of all touchpoints to create the entire experience. A successful service is one where the customer can experience the service as a whole, rather than a series of disconnected touchpoints.

As an example, Disney theme parks have been successful in creating unified experiences across touchpoints. Details both inside and outside the park are designed with a unified experience in mind. Disney characters roam the park, entrance tickets are printed with Disney characters on them; even the parking isles in the Disney parking lots are named after Disney characters. At every

touchpoint, guests feel enveloped in the Disney world. Customers should always feel like they're a part of the service at every step, to ensure the best customer-company relationship possible.

Music and service impressions

One of the strongest impressions in music is the very first. "...The first impression, which is so important... is completely dependent upon the validity of a presentation that eludes all controls" (Stravinsky, 1942/1970, p.133). This notion may be even more important in services. In fact, in customer surveys done by Marriott hotels, four of the five top factors that contribute to customer loyalty occur in the first ten minutes of interaction (Zeithaml, Bitner, and Gremler, 2006, p.124).

A series of actions could be taken to ensure a proper delivery of first impressions. In music, this is mostly done by ensuring that the performer is competent and well aware of the composer's intentions for the piece. This should also be true in services, where the service employees who are responsible for interacting with the customers should become masters of their elements (discussed in the Roles section).

Music and service styles

Musical styles are what differentiate composers from each other (and between performers as well). Similarly, in services, styles can be a great way for service providers to provide a means of differentiation from those that offer similar services. Many aspects of a service can contribute to its style; employee uniforms, physical space and décor, pace and speed of service, each detail has some attribute that can give different impressions to the customer.

For example, what sets Apple apart from other companies that offer the same products and services is that they have a unique style in which they conduct service. All of their stores are clean and modern; the display of their products gives off a very "museum-like appearance" (Zeithaml et al., 2006, p.323). Contrast this to a store like Circuit City, where the atmosphere is very different. Each has their own advantages, and styles are what need to be kept in mind when designers think about how they want their service portrayed to a customer.

Roles

There are three main roles associated with any musical performance: the composer, the performer, and the listener. These music roles lend themselves fittingly to parallels in service design (see Figure 2): composers could be thought of as service designers, performers as frontline staff of a service provider, and listeners as customers.

Figure 2: Role comparisons

The composer | service designer

I will discuss three traits of musical composers that are useful to think about as we analyze the role of a service designer: giving shape to ideas, being a master of elements, and creating possibilities for the unexpected.

Giving shape to ideas

The most basic role of a composer is to give shape to his musical ideas. “The process of artistic creation is always the same—from inwardness to lucidity” (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.43). Similarly in services, service designers are often the ones who shape the idea for a service. They are the ones who will think not only about the details of each touchpoint in a service, but also how all of these details fit into a whole service journey.

Consider Howard Shultz, now CEO of Starbucks. Before becoming CEO, he envisioned: “a company that would become a part of its customer’s lives... a familiar and welcoming refuge from work or home” (Gulati et al., 2002). The owner of Starbucks at the time did not share Mr. Schultz’s vision, so Mr. Schultz started his own company. In two years, Mr. Schultz’s company expanded to three locations, bought out Starbucks and Mr. Schultz became the major shareholder and CEO. This type of action is what embodies the role of the service designer. They think of ideas, and give shape and meaning to them.

Being a master of elements

To make great music, one must first be a master of musical elements. What rhythms will tell the perfect story? What instruments will carry the best voice? Being a master of elements allows the

composer to go beyond simply stringing sequences of notes together to form melodies; “the deeper the composer’s awareness of the basic elements of music, the more vital his imagination is likely to be” (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.58). Comparing this to service design, designers need to think about becoming a master of elements before taking on the bigger challenge of creating not only a competent service but one that customers will go back to out of personal desire rather than necessity.

The designers behind the Disney Resorts and Parks set a good example of how first mastering service elements can lead to innovating in other aspects. After implementing all the basics of the park (e.g., park layout, ride designs, etc.), they started thinking about details they could add to enhance the guest experience. Offerings of seemingly small things, like their talking and traveling trash cans that greet guests, are what makes the guest experience special and cannot be successful until the service basics are not only in place, but implemented well.

Creating possibilities for the unexpected

A successful composer has an ability to create music that contains qualities that connect to audiences in an unexpected, but pleasing manner. “Successive impressions must either maintain the level of intensity, of interest... or they must raise it. Otherwise... the tension relaxes, the ear becomes bored, and the music lags” (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.60). Similarly, the service designer must also maintain or raise the level of interest in their services. This will help push the service from satisfactory to outstanding.

For example, at every Ritz Carlton hotel, all employees are given \$2000 per guest to make a personal impact on a customer’s experience (CNN Money, 2004). These gestures were made possible because room was given in the design of the service to allow for it. These unexpected moments at the Ritz Carleton—the fancy birthday cake, or a surprise lavish anniversary gift waiting in your room—are those that create loyal customers, ones who will continue using a service because of one great moment they experienced at an earlier time.

The Performer | front-line employee

I will discuss three elements of a performer that are useful to think about when developing the role of the front-line employee: they give movement to a static idea, they are both an executant and interpreter, and they create the unexpected.

Giving movement to a static idea

The performer is the one who brings a composer's idea to life. "It is this essential and inherent quality of music—its fluidity...that has inevitably produced the performer" (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.66). Great performers provide effortless movement to a piece of music that would otherwise sit on paper. Frontline employees of any service serve exactly the same function. They are the ones responsible for bringing alive designers' ideas.

This is especially important when "the provider has discretion in determining the nature of the service and how it is received" (Zeithaml et al., 2006, p.63). Consider education; perhaps not thought of often enough as a service, yet is one of the most important. The idea of teaching a subject is standard across schools, but the role of the teacher in delivering an education to a student is the crucial area. The teacher not only has the responsibility to deliver information to their students, but also decides what and how they will deliver this knowledge. A great teacher will teach in a way that brings subject content to life.

Being an executant as well as an interpreter

When a performer becomes a master of elements, they can get past the technicalities of the performance and focus on giving the music its character. "It is [the performer's] task... to apply his imagination to discovering the musical gesture inherent in the composer's text" (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.73). In other words, the performer becomes an interpreter for the written music. "The first condition that must be fulfilled by anyone who aspires to the imposing title of interpreter, is that he be first of all a flawless executant" (Stravinsky, 1942/1970, p.127). These roles of executant and interpreter for a performer are important to think about, especially for the frontline staff of a service provider. In order to be successful at what they do, they need to know how to perform their expected duties without having to think much about them, in order to go a step beyond and provide an even higher level of care for the customer.

Imagine if you were a patient having blood drawn by a nurse. The nurse could be extremely nice, but if they appear nervous, or need to try five times to get the needle in, their pleasant manners will no longer matter—you will simply remember that the nurse was incompetent. On the other hand, experienced nurses who are technical experts will be able to go the extra mile with their patients and have their patients appreciate this extra effort.

Creating the unexpected

Musical performances are all about the unexpected. "[Mechanical reproduction] ceases to have interest for us, the instant we become aware of the fact of literal repetition, of mechanical

reproduction” (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.67). Paralleling this to service design, if a designer has created the opportunity for the unexpected, then it becomes the role of the frontline staff to bring unexpected delights to the customer. Frontline employees have the power to “make sure guests’ unexpressed wishes and needs are met” (Lovelock et al., 2006, p.312), creating loyal customers.

As an example, a letter of thanks was written to Lands’ End from a customer who tried to get a hold of a rare collector’s item that was no longer sold by the company. The customer service representative went out of her way to help track down some owners of these items to help acquire one. This is an example of a routine service engagement where the customer service employee could have simply said that they no longer sold that product, but instead went out of their way to deliver an unexpected surprise to the customer. This type of action is what will create loyal customers.

The Listener | customer

I will discuss the four stages of listening that a music listener has, which is useful to think about when approaching the customer of a service provider.

The four stages of listening

Figure 3: Sessions’ four stages of listening

According to Roger Sessions, there are four stages of a listener’s development: hearing, enjoying, understanding, and discriminating (see Figure 3). First, the listener hears and takes in the musical sounds (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.88). Next, the listener reacts to the music, which Sessions calls “enjoyment”. The listener then reaches musical understanding. They react to the music, but also start reproducing it to themselves. “He whistles it on the street, or simply “thinks” it to himself” (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.92). In this stage, the listener gathers musical senses, such as rhythm, articulation, or melody. Lastly, the listener discriminates. The listener will learn “to differentiate between lasting impressions and those which are fleeting, and between the musical experiences which give full satisfaction and those which only partly satisfy us” (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.94).

Applying this to services, Sessions’ four stages of listening could almost be used directly as four different stages of a customer’s service experience. First, at each service touchpoint, the customer simply takes in the service and surroundings. For example, a customer checking into a hotel for the night will take in things such as hotel lobby décor, pamphlets on the reception desk, hotel

receptionist uniforms, etc. Next, the customer will respond and react to these: he may see that the receptionist looks a little grumpy, and unconsciously becomes slightly grumpy himself. Next, the customer will replay these moments in his head. He may reflect upon the receptionist that was rude to him during the check-in process. Lastly, a service customer will learn to discriminate. They will learn by experience as to which services will give them satisfaction and which will not. An unhappy hotel customer may learn that paying more for a better hotel is worth the money.

This type of model is useful when designing services because it allows the designer to think about what a customer goes through. If a designer is aware of this process, more attention can be paid to the customer experience. “Service consumers are strongly influenced by the personal opinions of others... thus, understanding and controlling word-of-mouth communication is extremely important” (Zeithaml et al., 2006, p.67). By understanding the four stages of a customer’s experience, designers can hopefully support positive word-of-mouth communication for the customer.

As seen from the three different roles of a service, it is important that all three work well together to create a successful service. It is not just the composer or service designer that is responsible for creating the service; the frontline employees as well as the customers are also important in contributing to the service creation. “Not only are the performer and listener, in a real sense, re-experiencing and re-creating the musical thought of the composer, but they are, also in a real sense, adding to it” (Sessions, 1950/1967, p.102).

Tools

Music scores vs. service blueprints

Notation tools are often a way to tie all the involved people in a performance or service together. In music, the score is used by the composer to visually represent what his idea of a musical performance should sound like. In services, notations allows for the designer to mark exactly what should be included in the service and how the service should be performed. It allows for the service provider to follow this notation to deliver a solid service.

What is a service blueprint?

Composers use the music score as a tool for them to compose and record their musical thoughts. Service designers have a similar notation tool, called the service blueprint (see Figure 4). A service blueprint is a tool used by service designers to map out the service process. It was developed in

1984 by Lynn Shostack as a process control tool for services (Shostack, 1984). Since then, the blueprint has become more customer-focused, with the introduction of the blueprint as a plot between customer process and organizational structure in 1989. This more customer-focused blueprint is the one currently in use today by service designers and companies alike.

Figure 4: Example of part of a service blueprint for a typical overnight hotel stay

Why use service blueprints?

Blueprints are used for three main purposes: to design new services, to evaluate, or to improve existing services. There are many benefits to using a service blueprint in service design. Two main benefits are the following. First, service blueprints are a way to tie the different roles of a service together. The blueprint is an objective map that is fact-driven, and not opinion-driven (Zeithaml et al., 2006, p.267). It is a concrete visualization that everyone can contribute to and agree upon. Second, blueprints are also beneficial when thinking about its use as a guide for service employees. If designed properly, blueprints can be used to show a complete service process. Every action that a service employee should do, or could do, can be mapped onto the blueprint. It then becomes easier for a service manager to direct employees what to do. Without the completeness of a service

blueprint, the service performance could become an uncoordinated improvisation of what the employee thinks they should do without knowing the effect it will have on the rest of the service.

How music can play a role

Currently, blueprints cannot account for how customer satisfaction or emotions play a role in the service engagement. Since success in services depends largely on customer satisfaction, it seems natural for the service blueprint to be able to support the mapping of these customer's feelings. The problem is to figure out types of notation we could use to best map emotion and satisfaction. Work has been started in this area (Spraragen & Chan, 2008), but this is where music could play a big role, as music scores contain many types of expressive notation.

Future Direction

While a new notation system would greatly benefit the field, it would also be useful for service design to think about adopting an entire language of its own. Classical music is often described in terms of a particular set of features: rhythm, timbre, character, etc.—can we perhaps look to this to try and build our own language?

Also, as this paper focused solely on music as a source of inspiration, it is important to also look to other fields. Music provides a good beginning, but it is not the only field from which service design can profit. Fields such as dance, theater and film could also be fields to look at, as they all deal with complexities of performance. Looking to other fields will give service design a good grounding to start refining and solidifying itself as an established field.

Conclusion

Services will always exist as a part of our economy. If we want to create the best possible services for the public, then we should start looking at ways that service design could help. In this paper, I focused on music as a source of inspiration to discuss the aspects of service design that designers need to keep in mind. By looking at service engagements as performances, it becomes helpful to apply aspects of music performance that have been successful over the course of many centuries to the relatively new field of service design. Hopefully in shedding new light on services, service design can look ahead to being a more established and prominent field in the future.

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